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LEXICAL-SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF THE TERM “DIPLOMATIC” AND ITS USAGE IN VARIOUS LEXICAL-PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITHIN TEXTS

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Abstract

This article reveals the lexical and semantic meanings of the word “diplomatic”, which occurs frequently in diplomatic texts in English. At the same time, the occurrence of this word in diplomatic texts in English in the form of various lexical-phraseological units, the lexical and semantic properties of the meaning understood from them were analyzed on the basis of examples. Statistical data of lexical-phraseological units of the term “diplomatic” has been gathered in the following article.

Key words: diplomatic, lexical-phraseological units, lexical meaning of collocations, semantic meaning of diplomatic collocations.

Introduction

Diplomatic discourse is a form of communication that involves certain aspects. These include the correct selection and use of lexical units, which serve as indicators of the functional style of a particular discourse. In diplomatic communication, which is recognized as a special form of communication, one can observe the predominance of the terminological lexicon. This type of lexicon is used in speech and written texts in direct interaction with words in common use.

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In any discourse, semantically common words of general use can be distinguished as well as terminological lexicon. The main reason for this is that the terms and words in both groups have different meanings. Simply put, the terminological lexicon is limited to a specific social, economic, and political domain, while the common words represent concepts in everyday life.

Specific terms used in any discourse are used with their own meaning within the context in which they are used. That's why it is important to be very strict in terms of vocabulary. Terms can be incorporated into the vocabulary of a language as a separate part of it, as words with a limited meaning. The terminological lexicon is distinguished from other common words by a number of peculiarities. There are a number of linguistic theories. Some argue that terms should have a clear meaning, be functionally limited, not contain expressive or modal content, be stylistically distant from colorfulness, and instead be neutral and specific.

Today, the boundaries between the meaning of special terminological lexicon and the meaning of words in everyday life are being eroded. The emergence of factors related to the change of time and space, the change of the semantic meaning of special terms, leads to the emergence of polysemy more strongly.

The Russian scholar Shevchuk analyzed the semantic meanings of words and terms in the military, political, and diplomatic spheres, and gave an interpretation of the 7 semantic meanings of the word day in English. In addition, the word protocol has the following 3 semantic meanings in Russian: 1) Protocol (a type of document of international class); 2) a set of rules of conduct in public places, etiquette; 3) a protocol department under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. (Shevchuk,1983)

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In his dissertation, Safarov J.Sh examines the semantics of diplomatic lexemes and shows that they are used in compounds. He uses the word “diplomatic” as an example. He argued that the term is structurally and semantically composed of compounds, divided into two groups, namely, phraseological terminological compounds and free-relational compounds. According to the author, terminological compounds have a number of peculiar properties that indicate them as separate linguistic phenomena. First of all, they are related to realities that are outside the linguistic meaning of things and events, because they perform a direct nominative function. The formation of terminological compounds does not take place without departing from the semantic meaning of the components. Conversely, the components of a terminological compound retain their semantic independence in most cases. For example:

Diplomatic privileges and immunities - diplomatic privileges and immunities are exceptions to the general rule of international law that each sovereign state is supreme within its own boundaries and has jurisdiction over all persons and things found within its territories. These are, instead, exemptions of a diplomat- from national and local civil and criminal jurisdictions of the state to which: they are accredited. Diplomatic pr. and imm. include freedom from arrest, trial, civil suit, subpoena, and legal penalty ... (Plano, 1988)

Diplomatic – related to diplomacy (diplomacy: management of a country’s affairs by its agents abroad, and their control and monitor by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs at homecountry);

Immunity - safety, security (from disease, etc); exemption (from taxation, etc);

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Privilege - right or advantage available only to a person, class or rank, or the holder of a certain position.

In addition, Safarov J.Sh cites a number of word compounds related to the term “diplomatic”: *diplomatic action, diplomatic activity, diplomatic agent, diplomatic archives, diplomatic asylum, diplomatic body, diplomatic ceremonial, diplomatic channels, diplomatic circles, diplomatic climb-down, diplomatic conduct, diplomatic contacts, diplomatic corps, diplomatic correspondence, diplomatic courier, diplomatic efforts, diplomatic files, diplomatic formula, diplomatic law, diplomatic letters, diplomatic list, diplomatic mail, diplomatic manoeuvre, diplomatic means, diplomatic messenger, diplomatic mission, diplomatic note, diplomatic officer, diplomatic officials, diplomatic personal, diplomatic platform, diplomatic policy, diplomatic premises, diplomatic protocol, diplomatic rank, diplomatic records, diplomatic relations, diplomatic sell-out, diplomatic service, diplomatic settlement, diplomatic status, diplomatic support, diplomatic victory, diplomatic way-out, diplomatic with drawl.* (Safarov, 2000)

The information in diplomatic texts can be expressed differently depending on the lexical-pragmatic semantic properties. Therefore, a diplomatic text can be rendered using different linguistic mediums depending on the purpose and meaning of the thought. The structure of a text in the diplomatic field can be quite different from that of texts in the medical, technical, economic, sports, and social fields.

As we studied the dictionary definition of the word “diplomatic”, we learned that the Oxford English Dictionary defines it as follows:

1. related to the management of relations between countries;
2. the ability or display of skill in dealing with people in difficult situations (a synonym for politeness).

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The Cambridge English Dictionary gives the following meaning to the word:

1. diplomatic or related to the management of relations between countries: diplomatic negotiations, diplomatic relations, diplomatic ties, a diplomatic mission
2. to act in a way that does not lead to a violation of the law (fraud):

Ask him nicely - be diplomatic.

According to the Webster Dictionary , the term has the following meanings:

1. Paleography (the study of ancient manuscripts and inscriptions, the history of the creation of writing signs and their appearance (such as the style of appearance, the shape of letters, the type of written material);
2. corresponds to the original, matches the original; matches the original source;
3. related to or having to do with the art and practice of conducting negotiations between nations: related to or having to do with diplomacy or diplomats;
4. the ability to use reason and reconciliation in difficult situations.

These meanings are illustrated by examples from newspaper articles published in the United Kingdom and the United States:

Diplomatic sources say both men are under official protection. (Times Sunday Times, 2016)

A diplomatic source said: “The irony is that the royal family has used oil to slow down social change”. (Times Sunday Times, 2016)

China has made no such report, according to *diplomatic sources*. (Times Sunday Times, 2013)

Maybe being *diplomatic* and tactful would work better. (The Sun, 2015)

The move kicked off a tense *diplomatic standoff*.(Wall Street Journal, 2025)

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While analyzing texts and articles published in The Guardian, Wall Street Journal, and other magazines and newspapers, we further expanded the following lexical units that come with the word “diplomatic”: *a diplomatic standoff, a diplomatic effort, diplomatic gains, a diplomatic scramble, a diplomatic solution, diplomatic cables, diplomatic protection, diplomatic technique, diplomatic formulations, diplomatic marathon, diplomatic channels, diplomatic stops, a diplomatic mystery, a diplomatic task, diplomatic life and times, diplomatic practice, a diplomatic language, diplomatic hostages, diplomatic exchanges, a diplomatic answer, diplomatic record books, a diplomatic crisis, diplomatic pressure, diplomatic duplicity.*

We’ve been looking at a number of English magazines and it has been found out that the use of the word “diplomatic” in the English language has expanded significantly over the decades. In the European English-language magazine “The Diplomat” the term “diplomatic” was used 79 times in the second issue of 2022, 157 times in the first issue of 2023, 110 times in the first issue of 2024, and 123 times in the second issue of 2024. In the process of analysis, one can observe that the word “diplomatic” has a lexical relationship with words used in everyday life and is used in the form of lexical compounds. Based on the 10 selected issues of the magazine, the following combinations with the word “diplomatic” have been compiled: *diplomatic missions, diplomatic adviser, diplomatic community, diplomatic archives, diplomatic corps, diplomatic efforts, diplomatic relationship, diplomatic relations, diplomatic channels, diplomatic objectives, diplomatic sessions, diplomatic events, diplomatic conference, diplomatic undertaking, diplomatic collaboration, diplomatic ties, diplomatic activities, diplomatic circles, diplomatic career, diplomatic exchanges, diplomatic gathering, diplomatic*

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posting, diplomatic staff, diplomatic settings, diplomatic finesse, diplomatic endeavors, diplomatc adventure, diplomatic world, diplomatic husband, diplomatic service, diplomatic life, diplomatic spouse, diplomatic road, diplomatic representation, diplomatic landscape, diplomatic engagement, diplomatic journey, diplomatic envoys, diplomatic tactics, diplomatic footprint, diplomatic calendar, diplomatic discourse, diplomatic reception, diplomatic group, diplomatic touch, diplomatic representative, diplomatic camaraderie, diplomatic ceremony, diplomatic mandate, diplomatic law, diplomatic sales, diplomatic guests, diplomatic priorities, diplomatic luminary, diplomatic odyssey, diplomatic prowess, diplomatic achievement, diplomatic dialogue, diplomatic child, diplomatic trainee, diplomatic partner, diplomatic work, diplomatic resolution, diplomatic nature, diplomatic visits, diplomatic front, diplomatic practice, diplomatic family, diplomatic titles, diplomatic children, diplomatic kids, diplomatic pouch, diplomatic advantages, diplomatic arena, diplomatic unification, diplomatic magazine, diplomatic gift, diplomatic training, diplomatic experience, diplomatic leadership, diplomatic capitals, diplomatic approach, diplomatic academies, diplomatic training programs, diplomatic training institutions, diplomatic domain, diplomatic workforce, diplomatic skills, diplomatic and international relations training, diplomatic and international training institute, diplomatic and international training institute of the Netherlands, diplomatic practitioners, diplomatic delegation, diplomatic clients, diplomatic hub, diplomatic immunity, diplomatic vehicle, diplomatic buyers, diplomatic puzzle.

Conclusion

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It can be concluded that the semantic meaning of the word “diplomatic” has expanded dramatically over time. This process has seen a growing tendency for this word to enter into a lexical relationship not only with words and terms of the diplomatic sphere, but also with words used in everyday life. From the materials that have been studied, we have come to the conclusion that the lexical-semantic meaning of lexical units in English, such as protocol and diplomatic, has been greatly expanded, and in recent years, it is significantly noticed that these words are coming in very actively as part of various lexical combinations, not as isolated words. This in turn leads to an expansion of the semantic meaning of these words. Expansion of the lexical meaning of the above words by analyzing texts from several sources has been explained.

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